

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SPEECH ACTS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This study provides a comparative analysis of speech acts in English and Karakalpak, illustrating how linguistic intent reflects different cultural values.

Key words: Speech acts, a comparative study, distinct cultures, social norms, speaker's intent, communicative goal.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz va qoraqalpoq tillaridagi nutq aktlarining qiyosiy tahlilini taqdim etib, lisoniy niyat turli madaniy qadriyatlarini qanday aks ettirishini ko'rsatib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Nutq aktlari, qiyosiy tadqiqot, turli madaniyatlar, ijtimoiy normalar, so'zlovchining niyati, kommunikativ maqsad.

Аннотация: Данное исследование представляет собой сравнительный анализ речевых актов в английском и каракалпакском языках, иллюстрируя то, как лингвистическая интенция отражает различные культурные ценности.

Ключевые слова: Речевые акты, сравнительное исследование, различные культуры, социальные нормы, намерение говорящего, коммуникативная цель.

The study of speech acts is considered as one of the central pillars of pragmatics that is connected with linguacultural nuances of Turkic languages as Karakalpak, in comparison with English. Speech acts in English are dedicated to preserve personal boundaries while social hierarchy and collectivism are crucial in Karakalpak culture. Analyzing speech acts including the conceptosphere of speech in these two distinct cultures, demands a deep understanding of the underlying cultural values and social norms.

According to the theory of J.Austin speech acts can be categorized into three groups: locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary. [1] A locutionary act is about giving information correctly and simply that involves the production of an utterance with a specific linguistic structure. *"The sun is setting," said the gentleman. (Ch.Dickens)* This sentence depicts that there is no command or indirect request, only a straightforward act of informing is given. Also, in Karakalpak language a locutionary act can be used in sentences. *"Hawa rayi keskin ózgerdi, birden qatti suwiq keldi" – dedi Jamila. ("The weather changed drastically, a sudden cold snap arrived," said Jamila.)* This is simple informative form where a speech verb "dedi/said" is used and implies no specific action but conveys information. A comparative analysis of these examples in both languages locutionary acts can be the foundational layer of narrative communication. In English Subject-Verb-Object structure is utilized in order to give a concise information but in Karakalpak locutionary level can be more descriptive. Moreover, the illocutionary act focuses on speaker's communicative purposes such as commanding, asking, promising while the perlocutionary act impacts on receiver's emotions.

The communicative purpose is formed as a result of the speaker's specific intention and manifested through speech acts. The relationship between the speaker and the listener is established during the conversation based on a particular communicative context, finding its expression through the speaker's intent, the impact on the listener, and implicit meaning. Several scholars have reflected upon the communicative goal in their works. For instance, J. Searle explains the speaker's intention through illocutionary acts and categorizes them into five groups: Assertives (conveying information about factual matters); *Qizim jawirarli, suliw, shirayina qiziqpaytuğun adam joq, -dep izi úzilmeytuğun ángimeni saldırtıp sala berdi (G.Esemuratova). "My daughter is broad-shouldered and beautiful; there is no one who is not captivated by her beauty," she said, launching into an endless stream of*

praise). Directives (denoting actions such as commanding or requesting); Commissives (denoting future actions or obligations, or promising to perform or abstain from an act); Expressives (expressing the internal feelings or psychological state of the speaker); *Bári de umit bolar, -dep Ómirbek kempirine táselle aytp, janina barıp jılı sóylep kempiriniń kewlin alıp biraz otrdı.* (G.Esemuratova) (*All will be forgotten," Omirbek said, comforting his old wife; he sat beside her for a while, speaking warmly to soothe her heart*). Declarations (speech acts that bring about a change in the institutional state of affairs) [2]; *Men usı klassta balalardıń aldında aytarımdı aytıwım kerek.* (G.Esemuratova) (*I must say what I have to say here, in this classroom, in front of the children*). These examples in Karakalpak discourse represent both universal pragmatic functions and linguacultural characteristics, often differs from English models in terms of social indexing. The illocutionary acts perform a fundamental role in realizing the speaker's communicative goal. Their pragmatic properties are determined through their illocutionary force and pragmatic impact.

Illocutionary verbs that clarify pragmatic meaning are viewed as tools that enable the emergence of an effect within speech. They are considered significant during the speech act, as they clearly and distinctly demonstrate the goal, content, and illocutionary force of the communicative interaction [3]. This is vividly illustrated in the following literary context: *"Anası asxanağa shaqırıp: "Seni Orazımbettiń balasına ayttırıp kelipti, ol jigit penen tillesip kórdiń be, ózi?" – dep soraǵanda quwǵaninan tamaǵı qurǵap, tilinen sóz shıqqay qaldı."* (K.Karimov) (*"When her mother called her to the kitchen and asked: 'They have come to ask for your hand for Orazimbet's son; have you actually spoken with that young man yourself?' her throat went dry with joy, and she remained speechless."*) In this example, the illocutionary force is directed toward a speech act presented in the form of a question. Here, pragmatic factors indicate not only the speaker's (the mother's) intent to receive information but also the broader communicative situation. Furthermore, it contains an implicit pragmatic meaning; specifically, it inquires whether the listener has approached this situation with serious attention or personal interest. The silence of the daughter in response to the mother's question also functions as a perlocutionary effect, where emotional overwhelm inhibits the locutionary act. In addition to this example, a similar illocutionary act can be seen in English works: *"An unhappy alternative is before you, Elizabeth. From this day you must be a stranger to one of your parents. Your mother will never see you again if you do not marry Mr. Collins, and I will never see you again if you do."* (J.Austen) Here, the illocutionary force serves as paradoxical advice that consists of the illocutionary intent of father to support daughter's autonomy by using irony. By comparing these examples, it is evidently known that marriage-related discourse is universal but strategies of linguistics are dissimilar with each other.

In conclusion, the pragmatic analysis of speech acts in English and Karakalpak languages has their own differences and similarities. It should be noted that understanding a language is not about a grammar, it is understanding hidden meanings of the sentences by pragmatic and cultural viewpoints.

References:

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3. Sh. Safarov. (2015). *Semantika [Study guide]*. Toshkent. p. 86.